

Some Operators in Kasaj Topological Spaces

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Abstract

We initiate an attributes of kasaj border, kasaj frontier and kasaj exterior by utilizing the idea of kasaj open sets, and study their kasaj topological properties. We give relation between kasaj derived sets, kasaj border, kasaj frontier and kasaj exterior. Also introduced the properties of $KS_{gs}(KS_{sg})$ -border, $KS_{gs}(KS_{sg})$ -frontier and $KS_{gs}(KS_{sg})$ -exterior are studied.

Keywords: $KS_{gs}(KS_{sg})$ -border, $KS_{gs}(KS_{sg})$ -frontier, $KS_{gs}(KS_{sg})$ -exterior.

1. Introduction

In 2020, Rachchh and Ghanchi [3] introduced partial extension of micro topological space namely kasaj topological spaces. Also in above year [5] defined kasaj generalized closed sets in kasaj topological spaces and obtained some basic results. In 2022, Prakash et al. [1] introduced and studied the concept of $KS_{gs}(KS_{sg})$ -closed sets. Further reference Sathishmohan et al. [2] is used to study the following paper.

The reason for this paper is to examine about a concepts of operators namely Kasaj border, Kasaj frontier and kasaj exterior by utilizing the idea of kasaj open sets and extends this idea to study $KS_{gs}(KS_{sg})$ -border, $KS_{gs}(KS_{sg})$ -frontier and $KS_{gs}(KS_{sg})$ -exterior of a set using kasaj topological properties.

NOTATIONS: Throughout this paper work, we use this symbols:

- (i) KSTS \longrightarrow kasaj topological space.
- (ii) KS-O \longrightarrow kasaj-open.
- (iii) KS-C \longrightarrow kasaj-closed.

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- (iv) $KS_{br} \longrightarrow$ kasaj border.
- (v) $KS_{sbr} \longrightarrow$ kasaj semi border.
- (vi) $KS_{gbr} \longrightarrow$ kasaj generalized border.
- (vii) $KS_{gsbr} \longrightarrow$ kasaj generalized semi border.
- (viii) $KS_{sgbr} \longrightarrow$ kasaj semi generalized border.
- (ix) $KS_{ext} \longrightarrow$ kasaj exterior.
- (x) $KS_{sext} \longrightarrow$ kasaj semi exterior.
- (xi) $KS_{gext} \longrightarrow$ kasaj generalized exterior.
- (xii) $KS_{gsext} \longrightarrow$ kasaj generalized semi exterior.
- (xiii) $KS_{sgext} \longrightarrow$ kasaj semi generalized exterior.
- (xiv) $KS_{fr} \longrightarrow$ kasaj frontier.
- (xv) $KS_{sfr} \longrightarrow$ kasaj semi frontier.
- (xvi) $KS_{gfr} \longrightarrow$ kasaj generalized frontier.
- (xvii) $KS_{gsfr} \longrightarrow$ kasaj generalized semi frontier.
- (xviii) $KS_{sgfr} \longrightarrow$ kasaj semi generalized frontier.
- (xix) $KS_{dr} \longrightarrow$ kasaj derived.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [3] Let $(U, \tau_R(X))$ be a nano topological space. Then kasaj topology is defined by

$$KS_R(X) = \{(K \cap S) \cup (K' \cap S') : K, K' \in \tau_R(X), \text{ fixed } S, S' \notin \tau_R(X), S \cup S' = U\}.$$

The kasaj topology $KS_R(X)$ satisfies the following postulates:

- (i) $U, \phi \in KS_R(X)$
- (ii) The union of elements of any subcollection of $KS_R(X)$ is in $KS_R(X)$
- (iii) The intersection of any finite subcollection of elements of $KS_R(X)$ is in $KS_R(X)$

Then $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ is called KSTS and the members of $KS_R(X)$ are called $KS - O$ set and the complement of a $KS - O$ set is called a $KS - C$ set.

Definition 2.2. [3] The kasaj closure and the kasaj interior of a set P is denoted by $KS_{cl}(P)$ and $KS_{int}(P)$, respectively. It is defined by

$$KS_{cl}(P) = \bigcap \{Q : P \subseteq Q, Q \text{ is } KS - C\},$$

and

$$KS_{int}(P) = \bigcup \{Q : Q \subseteq P, Q \text{ is } KS - O\}.$$

Remark 2.3. [3] For a KSTS $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$:

- (i) $KS_{int}(P)$ is the largest $KS - O$ set contained in P .
- (ii) $KS_{cl}(P)$ is the smallest $KS - C$ set containing P

Definition 2.4. [3] For any two subsets P, Q of U in a KSTS $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$:

- (i) P is a $KS - C$ set iff $KS_{cl}(P) = P$.
- (ii) P is a $KS - O$ set iff $KS_{int}(P) = P$.
- (iii) If $P \subseteq Q$, then $KS_{int}(P) \subseteq KS_{int}(Q)$ and $KS_{cl}(P) \subseteq KS_{cl}(Q)$.
- (iv) $KS_{cl}(KS_{cl}(P)) = KS_{cl}(P)$ and $KS_{int}(KS_{int}(P)) = KS_{int}(P)$.
- (v) $KS_{cl}(P) \cup KS_{cl}(Q) \supseteq KS_{cl}(P \cup Q)$.
- (vi) $KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{int}(Q) \supseteq KS_{int}(P \cup Q)$.
- (vii) $KS_{cl}(P \cap Q) \subseteq KS_{cl}(P) \cap KS_{cl}(Q)$.
- (viii) $KS_{int}(P \cap Q) \subseteq KS_{int}(P) \cap KS_{int}(Q)$.
- (ix) $KS_{cl}(P) = [KS_{int}(P)]^c$.
- (x) $KS_{int}(P) = [KS_{cl}(P)]^c$.

Definition 2.5. [4] Let $P \subseteq U$. Then P is $KS - C$ in $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$,

- (i) P is a $KS - C$ set iff $P = KS_{cl}(P)$.
- (ii) P is a $KS - O$ set iff $P = KS_{int}(P)$.

Definition 2.6. [3] For any two subsets P, Q of U in a KSTS $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$, the KS -semi-closure and the KS -semi-interior of a set P are denoted by $KS_{scl}(P)$ and $KS_{sint}(P)$, respectively, defined by

$$KS_{scl}(P) = \bigcap \{Q : P \subseteq Q, Q \text{ is } KS\text{-semi-closed}\},$$

$$KS_{sint}(P) = \bigcup \{Q : Q \subseteq P, Q \text{ is } KS\text{-semi-open}\}$$

Definition 2.7. [3] The KS -generalized closure of P is defined as the intersection of all KS_g -closed sets containing P . It is denoted by $KS_{gcl}(P)$.

Definition 2.8. [3] The KS -generalized interior of P is defined as the union of all KS_g -open sets containing P . It is denoted by $KS_{gint}(P)$.

Definition 2.9. [3] Let $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ be a KSTS. Then P is said to be KS -generalized neighbourhood (briefly, KS_g -nbhd) of a point x of U if there exists KS_g -open set F containing x such that $x \in F \subseteq P$.

3. KS -Border of a set.

In this section, we define and study about KS -Border of sets and obtain some of their properties.

Definition 3.1. Let P be subset of KSTS $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$,

- (i) KS -broder of P is defined by $KS_{br}(P) = P - KS_{int}(P)$.
- (ii) KS -semi-broder of P is defined by $KS_{sbr}(P) = P - KS_{sint}(P)$.
- (iii) KS -g-broder of P is defined by $KS_{gbr}(P) = P - KS_{gint}(P)$.

(iv) KS-gs-broder of P is defined by $KS_{gsbr}(P) = P - KS_{gsint}(P)$.

(v) KS-sg-broder of P is defined by $KS_{sgbr}(P) = P - KS_{sgint}(P)$.

Proposition 3.2. Let P be subset of U , $KS_{br}(P) \subseteq P$.

Theorem 3.3. In a KSTS $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ for any subset P of U , the following statement hold:

(i) $KS_{br}(\phi) = KS_{br}(U) = \phi$.

(ii) $KS_{br}(P) \subseteq P$.

(iii) $KS_{int}(P) = P - KS_{br}(P)$.

(iv) $KS_{br}(P) = P \cap KS\text{-cl}(U) - P$.

Proof. (i), (ii) and (iii) follow from the Definition 4.1. To prove (iv):

$$KS_{br}(P) = P - KS_{int}(P) \cap U - KS_{int}(P) = P \cap KS - cl(U) - P = U - KS_{int}(P).$$

Hence (iv) is proved. □

Theorem 3.4. In a KSTS $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ for any subset P of U , the following statements holds:

(i) $P = KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{br}(P)$.

(ii) $KS_{int}(P) \cap KS_{br}(P) = \phi$.

(iii) P is $KS - O$ iff $KS_{br}(P) = \phi$.

(iv) $KS_{br}(KS_{int}(P)) = \phi$.

(v) $KS_{int}(KS_{br}(P)) = \phi$.

(vi) $KS_{br}(KS_{br}(P)) = KS_{br}(P)$.

Proof. (i) Let $x \in P$. If $x \in KS_{int}(P)$ then $P \subseteq KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{br}(P)$. If $x \notin KS_{int}(P)$, then by the definition of $KS_{br}(P)$, $x \in KS_{br}(P)$. Hence $x \in KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{br}(P)$ and so, $P \subseteq KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{br}(P)$. On the other hand, Since $KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{br}(P) \subseteq P$. Therefore $P = KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{br}(P)$.

(ii) Suppose $KS_{int}(P) \cap KS_{br}(P) \neq \phi$. Let $x \in KS_{int}(P) \cap KS_{br}(P)$. Then $x \in KS_{int}(P)$ and $x \in KS_{br}(P)$. Since $KS_{br}(P) = P - KS_{int}(P)$, $x \in P$ and $x \notin P$. This is the contradiction. Hence $KS_{int}(P) \cap KS_{br}(P) = \phi$.

(iii) Necessity: Suppose P is $KS - O$. By the definition 2.5 (ii), $KS_{int}(P) = P$. Now, $KS_{br}(P) = P - KS_{int}(P) = P - P = \phi$. Sufficiency: Suppose $KS_{br}(P) = \phi$. This implies, $P - KS_{int}(P) = \phi$. Therefore $P = KS_{int}(P)$ and hence P is $KS - O$.

(iv) By the definition of KS-border of a set, $KS_{br}(P)(KS_{int}(P)) = KS_{int}(P) - KS_{int}(KS_{int}(P))$. By the definition 2.5, $KS_{br}(P)(KS_{int}(P)) = KS_{int}(P) - KS_{int}(P)$. $KS_{br}(P)(KS_{int}(P)) = \phi$.

(v) Let $x \in KS_{int}(KS_{br}(P))$. Since $KS_{br}(P) \subseteq P$. By Property 3.3, $KS_{int}(KS_{br}(P)) \subseteq KS_{int}(P)$. Hence $x \in KS_{int}(P)$. Since, $KS_{int}(KS_{br}(P)) \subseteq KS_{br}(P)$, then $x \in KS_{br}(P)$. Therefore $x \in KS_{int}(P) \cap KS_{br}(P)$. By (ii), $x = \phi$. It follows that $KS_{int}(KS_{br}(P)) = \phi$.

(vi) By the definition of KS-border of a set, $(KS_{br}(P)) = KS_{br}(P) - KS_{int}(KS_{br}(P))$. By (v) $KS_{br}(KS_{br}(P)) = KS_{br}(P) - \phi$. Hence $KS_{br}(KS_{br}(P)) = KS_{br}(P)$. □

4. KS-Exterior of a set

In this section, we define and study about KS-Exterior of sets and obtain some of their properties.

Definition 4.1. Let P be a subset of a KSTS $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$. Then:

- (i) KS-interior of $U - P$ is called the KS-exterior of P and it is denoted by $KS_{ext}(P)$. That is, $KS_{ext}(P) = KS_{int}(U - P)$ or $KS_{ext}(P) = KS_{int}(P^c)$.
- (ii) KS-semi-interior of $U - P$ is called the KS-semi-exterior of P and it is denoted by $KS_{sext}(P)$. That is, $KS_{sext}(P) = KS_{sint}(U - P)$ or $KS_{sext}(P) = KS_{sint}(P^c)$.
- (iii) KS-g-interior of $U - P$ is called the KS-g-exterior of P and it is denoted by $KS_{gext}(P)$. That is, $KS_{gext}(P) = KS_{gint}(U - P)$ or $KS_{gext}(P) = KS_{gint}(P^c)$.
- (iv) KS-gs-interior of $U - P$ is called the KS-gs-exterior of P and it is denoted by $KS_{gsext}(P)$. That is, $KS_{gsext}(P) = KS_{gsint}(U - P)$ or $KS_{gsext}(P) = KS_{gsint}(P^c)$.
- (v) KS-sg-interior of $U - P$ is called the KS-sg-exterior of P and it is denoted by $KS_{sgext}(P)$. That is, $KS_{sgext}(P) = KS_{sgint}(U - P)$ or $KS_{sgext}(P) = KS_{sgint}(P^c)$.

Corollary 4.2. $KS_{ext}(P) = (KS_{cl}(P))^c$ from this, we conclude that $KS_{int}(P) = KS_{ext}(P^c) = (KS_{cl}(P^c))^c$.

Theorem 4.3. For a subset P of a KSTS U , the following conditions are true,

- (i) $KS_{ext}(P)$ is $KS - O$.
- (ii) $KS_{ext}(P) = U - KS_{cl}(P)$.
- (iii) $KS_{ext}(KS_{ext}(P)) = KS_{int}(KS_{cl}(P))$.
- (iv) If $P \subseteq Q$ then $KS_{ext}(Q) \subseteq KS_{ext}(P)$.
- (v) $KS_{ext}(P) \cap KS_{ext}(Q) \subseteq KS_{ext}(P \cap Q)$.
- (vi) $KS_{ext}(P \cup Q) \subseteq KS_{ext}(P) \cap KS_{ext}(Q)$.
- (vii) $KS_{ext}(U) = \phi$ and $KS_{ext}(\phi) = U$.
- (viii) $KS_{ext}(P) = KS_{ext}(U - KS_{ext}(P))$.
- (ix) $P \cap KS_{ext}(P) = \phi$.

Proof. (i) Now $KS_{int}(KS_{ext}(P)) = KS_{int}(KS_{ext}(U - P)) = KS_{int}(U - P) = KS_{ext}(P) \Rightarrow KS_{ext}(P)$ is $KS - O$.

(ii) $KS_{ext}(P) = KS_{int}(U - P) = U - KS_{cl}(P)$.

(iii) $KS_{ext}(KS_{ext}(P)) = KS_{ext}(U - KS_{cl}(P))$. By (ii), $KS_{int}(U - (U - KS_{cl}(P))) = KS_{int}(KS_{cl}(P))$.

(iv) If $P \subseteq Q$, then $(U - Q) \subseteq (U - P) \Rightarrow KS_{int}(U - Q) \subseteq KS_{int}(U - P)$. That is $KS_{ext}(Q) \subseteq KS_{ext}(P)$.

(v) We have $(P \cap Q) \subseteq P$, $(P \cap Q) \subseteq Q \Rightarrow KS_{ext}(P) \subseteq KS_{ext}(P \cap Q)$ and $KS_{ext}(Q) \subseteq KS_{ext}(P \cap Q) \Rightarrow KS_{ext}(P) \cap KS_{ext}(Q) \subseteq KS_{ext}(P \cap Q)$.

(vi) $KS_{ext}(P \cup Q) = KS_{int}(U - (P \cup Q)) = KS_{int}((U - P) \cap (U - Q)) \subseteq KS_{int}(U - P) \cap KS_{int}(U - Q) \subseteq KS_{ext}(P) \cap KS_{ext}(Q)$. Therefore $KS_{ext}(P \cup Q) \subseteq KS_{ext}(P) \cap KS_{ext}(Q)$.

- (vii) Follows from the Definition 4.1.
- (viii) $KS_{ext}(U - KS_{ext}(P)) = KS_{int}(U - KS_{ext}(P)) = KS_{int}(KS_{ext}(P) = KS_{int}(KS_{int}(U - P)) = KS_{int}(U - P) = KS_{ext}(P)$.
- (ix) Obvious.

□

5. KS-Frontier of a set

In this section, we define and study about KS-frontier of sets and show that some of their properties.

Definition 5.1. For a subset P of U in a KSTS $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$,

- (i) KS-frontier $(KS_{fr}(P))$ if $KS_{cl}(P) - KS_{int}(P)$.
- (ii) KS_s -frontier $(KS_{sfr}(P))$ if $KS_{scl}(P) - KS_{sint}(P)$.
- (iii) KS_g -frontier $(KS_{gfr}(P))$ if $KS_{gcl}(P) - KS_{gint}(P)$.
- (iv) KS_{gs} -frontier $(KS_{gsfr}(P))$ if $KS_{gscl}(P) - KS_{gsint}(P)$.
- (v) KS_{sg} -frontier $(KS_{sgfr}(P))$ if $KS_{sgcl}(P) - KS_{sgint}(P)$.

Theorem 5.2. Let P be a subset of U . Then P is $KS - C$ iff $KS_{fr}(P) \subseteq P$.

Proof. Necessity: Suppose P is $KS - C$. By Definition 2.5 (i), $KS_{cl}(P) = P$. Now, $KS_{fr}(P) = KS_{cl}(P) - KS_{int}(P) = P - KS_{int}(P) \subseteq P$. Hence, $KS_{fr}(P) \subseteq P$.
 Sufficiency: Assume that $KS_{fr}(P) \subseteq P$. Then $KS_{cl}(P) - KS_{int}(P) \subseteq P$. Since $KS_{int}(P) \subseteq P$. We conclude that $KS_{cl}(P) \subseteq P$. Also $P \subseteq KS_{cl}(P)$. Therefore $KS_{cl}(P) = P$ and hence P is $KS - C$. □

Theorem 5.3. Let X be a KSTS and let $P \subseteq U$. Then a point x in U is KS-frontier point of P if and only if every neighbourhood of x intersects both P and P^c .

Proof. We have $x \in KS_{fr}(P) \Leftrightarrow x \notin KS_{int}(P)$ and $x \notin KS - ext(P) = KS_{int}(P^c) \Leftrightarrow$ neither P nor P^c is a KS-nhd of $x \Leftrightarrow$ no KS-nhd of x can be contained in P or in $P^c \Leftrightarrow$ every KS-nhd of x intersects both P and P^c . □

Corollary 5.4. $KS_{fr}(P) = KS_{fr}(P^c)$.

Proof. We have $x \in KS_{fr}(P) \Leftrightarrow$ every KS-nhd of x intersects both P and $P^c \Leftrightarrow$ every KS-nhd of x intersects both $(P^c)^c$ and $P^c \Leftrightarrow x \in KS_{fr}(P^c)$. □

Theorem 5.5. Let P be any subset of a KSTS $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$. Then $KS_{int}(P)$, $KS_{ext}(P)$ and $KS_{fr}(P)$ are disjoint and $U = KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{ext}(P) \cup KS_{fr}(P)$. Further $KS_{fr}(P)$ is $KS - C$ set.

Proof. By Definition 5.1, also $KS_{int}(P) \subseteq P$ and $KS_{int}(P^c) = P^c$. Since $P \cap P^c = \phi$, it follows that $KS_{int} \cap KS_{ext}(P) = KS_{int}(P) \cap KS_{int}(P^c) = \phi$. Again by the definition of frontier, we have $x \in KS_{fr}(P) \Leftrightarrow x \in KS_{int}(P)$ and $x \notin KS_{ext}(P) \Leftrightarrow x \notin KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{ext}(P) \Leftrightarrow x \in [KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{ext}(P)]^c$. Thus $KS_{fr}(P) = [KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{ext}(P)]^c \rightarrow (1)$ it follows that $KS_{fr}(P) \cap [KS_{int}(P)] = \phi$ and $KS_{fr}(P) \cap KS_{ext}(P) = \phi$ and $U = KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{ext}(P) \cup KS_{fr}(P)$. Since $KS_{int}(P)$ and $KS_{ext}(P)$ are open sets, we see from(1) that $KS_{fr}(P)$ is $KS - C$ set. □

Theorem 5.6. For a subset P of space U , the following conditions are true:

- (i) $KS_{cl}(P) = KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{fr}(P)$.

- (ii) $KS_{int}(P) \cap KS_{fr}(P) = \phi$.
- (iii) $KS_{fr}(P) = KS_{cl}(P) \cap KS_{cl}(U) - P$.
- (iv) $KS_{fr}(P) = KS_{fr}(U - P)$.
- (v) $KS_{fr}(P) \subseteq KS - C$.
- (vi) $KS_{fr}(KS_{fr}(P)) \subseteq KS_{fr}(P)$.
- (vii) $KS_{fr}(KS_{int}(P)) \subseteq KS_{fr}(P)$.
- (viii) $KS_{fr}(P) \supseteq KS_{fr}(KS_{cl}(P))$.
- (ix) $KS_{int}(P) = P - KS_{fr}(P)$.

Proof. (i) $KS_{int}(P) \subseteq KS_{cl}(P)$ and $KS_{fr}(P) \subseteq KS_{cl}(P)$ thus $KS_{int}(P) \cap KS_{fr}(P) \subseteq KS_{cl}(P)$. Let $x \in KS_{cl}(P)$. Suppose $x \notin KS_{fr}(P)$. Then $x \in KS_{int}(P)$. Hence $KS_{cl}(P) \subseteq KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{fr}(P)$. It follows that, $KS_{cl}(P) = KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{fr}(P)$.

- (ii) Suppose $KS_{int}(P) \cap KS_{fr}(P) \neq \phi$. Let $x \in KS_{int}(P) \cap KS_{fr}(P)$. Then $x \in KS_{int}(P)$ and $x \in KS_{fr}(P)$, which is impossible to $x \in KS_{int}(P)$ and also $x \in KS_{fr}(P)$, since $KS_{fr}(P) = KS_{cl}(P) - KS_{int}(P)$. Hence, $KS_{int}(P) \cap KS_{fr}(P) = \phi$.
- (iii) Since $KS_{cl}(U) - P = U - KS_{int}(P)$, we get $KS_{cl}(P) \cap KS_{cl}(U) - P = KS_{cl}(P) \cap U - KS_{int}(P) = (KS_{cl}(P) \cap U) - (KS_{cl}(P) \cap KS_{int}(P)) = KS_{cl}(P) - KS_{int}(P) = KS_{fr}(P)$.
- (iv) By [iii], $KS_{fr}(P) = KS_{cl}(P) \cap KS_{cl}(U) - P = KS_{fr}(U) - P$.
- (v) Now, $KS_{cl}(KS_{fr}(P)) = KS_{cl}(KS_{cl}(P) \cap KS_{cl}(U) - P) \subseteq KS_{cl}(P) \cap KS_{cl}(U) - P = KS_{fr}(P)$. That is $KS_{cl}(KS_{fr}(P)) \subseteq KS_{fr}(P)$. Also $KS_{fr}(P) \subseteq KS_{cl}(KS_{fr}(P))$. Therefore $KS_{cl}(KS_{fr}(P)) = KS_{fr}(P)$ and hence $KS_{fr}(P)$ is KS-C.
- (vi) By [v], $KS_{fr}(P)$ is KS-C and by above theorem, $KS_{fr}(KS_{fr}(P)) \subseteq KS_{fr}(P)$.
- (vii) By the definition of KS-frontier, $KS_{fr}(KS_{int}(P)) = KS_{cl}(KS_{int}(P)) - KS_{int}(KS_{int}(P)) \subseteq KS_{cl}(P) - KS_{int}(P) = KS_{fr}(P)$. Hence, $KS_{fr}(KS_{int}(P)) \subseteq KS_{fr}(P)$.
- (viii) By the definition of KS-frontier, $KS_{fr}(KS_{cl}(P)) = KS - cl(KS_{cl}(P)) - KS_{int}(KS_{cl}(P)) \subseteq KS_{cl}(P) - KS_{int}(P) = KS_{fr}(P)$. Hence, $KS_{fr}(P) \supseteq KS_{fr}(KS_{cl}(P))$.
- (ix) Now $P - KS_{fr}(P) = P - KS_{cl}(P) - KS_{int}(P) = P \cap ((U - KS_{cl}(P)) \cup (KS_{int}(P))) = \phi \cup KS_{int}(P) = KS_{int}(P)$. Hence $KS_{int}(P) = P - KS_{fr}(P)$. □

Theorem 5.7. Let P be a subset of U is $KS - C$, then $KS_{br}(P) = KS_{fr}(P)$.

Proof. Let P be a $KS - C$ subset of U . Then by Definition 2.5 (i) $KS_{cl}(P) = P$. Now, $KS_{fr}(P) = KS_{cl}(P) - KS_{int}(P) = P - KS_{int}(P) = KS_{br}(P)$. □

6. Relations between KS-closure, KS-interior and KS-frontier

Theorem 6.1. Let $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ be a KSTS and let $P \subset U$. Then:

- (i) $KS_{int}(P) = (KS_{cl}(P^c))^c$.
- (ii) $KS_{cl}(P^c) = (KS_{int}(P))^c$.
- (iii) $KS_{cl}(P) = (KS_{int}(P^c))^c$.

Proof. (i) From Corollary 4.3, it is obvious.

- (ii) Taking complements in (1), $(KS_{int}(P))^c = ((KS_{cl}(P^c))^c)^c = (KS_{cl}(P^c))^c$ [Note that $(S^c)^c = S$ for any set S].
- (iii) By (ii), $KS_{cl}(P^c) = (KS_{int}(P))^c$. Replacing P by P^c in this, we get $KS_{cl}((P^c)^c) = (KS_{int}(P^c))^c$ or $KS_{cl}(P) = (KS_{int}(P^c))^c$. Hence $KS_{cl}(P) = (KS_{int}(P^c))^c$ [Therefore $(P^c)^c = P$].

□

Theorem 6.2. Let $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ be a KSTS and let $Q \subseteq U$. Then $KS_{cl}(A) = KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{fr}(P)$.

Proof. By Definition 2.3 of $KS_{cl}(P)$, we have $KS_{cl}(P) = \bigcap \{Q : P \subset Q, Q \text{ is } KS-C\}$ and $(KS_{cl}(P))^c = \bigcup \{Q : Q \subset P, Q \text{ is } KS-O\} = KS_{ext}(P)$. By theorem $((KS_{cl}(P))^c)^c = (KS_{ext}(P))^c = KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{fr}(P)$. Hence $KS_{cl}(P) = KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{fr}(P)$. □

Corollary 6.3. $KS_{fr}(KS_{cl}(P)) \subseteq P$.

Corollary 6.4. $KS_{cl}(P) = P \cup KS_{fr}(P)$.

Proof. Since $P \subseteq KS_{cl}(P)$ and $KS_{fr}(P) \subseteq KS_{cl}(P)$, we have $P \cup KS_{fr}(P) \subseteq KS_{cl}(P)$. \rightarrow (1) Also $KS_{fr}(P) = (KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{ext}(P))^c = KS_{int}(P) \cap (KS_{ext}(P))^c$. Again since $KS_{int}(P) \subseteq P$ and $KS_{cl}(P) = KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{fr}(P)$, it follows that $KS_{cl}(P) \subseteq P \cup KS_{fr}(P) \rightarrow$ (2) From (1) and (2), we get $KS_{cl}(P) = P \cup KS_{fr}(P)$. □

Theorem 6.5. Every $KS-C$ subset of KSTS is the disjoint union of its interior and frontier, in the sense, that it contains these sets, they are disjoint and it is their union.

Proof. Let P be $KS-C$ subset of a KSTS so that $KS_{cl}(P) = P$. Hence by (6.2), $P = KS_{int}(P) \cup KS_{fr}(P)$. Also by (5.7), $KS_{int}(P) \cap KS_{fr}(P) = \phi$. □

Theorem 6.6. Let P be any subset of KSTS of $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$, then:

- (i) $KS_{sfr}(P) \subseteq KS_{scl}(P) \cap P^c - KS_{sint}(P)$.
- (ii) $KS_{int}(P) = P - KS_{sfr}(P)$.

Proof. (i) We have $KS_{sfr}(P) \subseteq [KS_{sint}(P) \cup KS_{sint}(P)]^c \subseteq KS_{sint}(P^c) \cap [KS_{sint}(P)]^c \subseteq ((KS_{scl}(P^c))^c)^c \cup (KS_{scl}(P^c))^c$ [by (8.3)] $\subseteq KS_{scl}(P^c) \cap KS_{scl}(P)$. Now $(KS_{scl}(P) \subseteq KS_{scl}(P^c) \subseteq KS_{scl}(P) - (KS_{scl}(P^c))^c \subseteq KS_{scl}(P) - KS_{sint}(P)$ by (8.3) Hence $KS_{sfr}(P) \subseteq KS_{scl}(P) \cap P^c \subseteq KS_{scl}(P) - KS_{sint}(P)$.

- (ii) $P - KS_{sfr}(P) \subseteq P - (KS_{scl}(P) - KS_{sint}(P))$ by (i) $\subseteq KS_{sint}(P)$

□

Theorem 6.7. Let P be any subset of KSTS of $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$, then:

- (i) $[KS_{gfr}(P)]^c \subseteq KS_{gint}(P) \cup KS_{gint}(P^c)$.
- (ii) $KS_{gfr}(KS_{gint}(P)) \subseteq KS_{gfr}(P)$.

$$(iii) \quad KS_{gfr}(KS_{gcl}(P)) \subseteq KS_{gfr}(P).$$

Proof. (i) We have $[KS_{gfr}(P)]^c \subseteq [KS_{gcl}(P) \cap (KS_{gcl}(P^c))]^c$ [by (10.6) (1)]
 $\subseteq [KS_{gcl}(P)]^c \cup [KS_{gcl}(P^c)]^c$. [by(8.3)]
 $[KS - gcl(P^c)]^c \subseteq KS_{gint}(P)$ and So, $KS_{gint}[P^c] \subseteq [KS_{gint}(P)]^c \subseteq [KS_{gcl}(P^c)]^c$
 $\subseteq [KS_{gcl}(P^c)]^c \subseteq [KS_{gcl}(P)]^c$.
 Therefore $[KS_{gfr}(P)]^c \subseteq KS_{gint}(P^c) \cup KS_{gint}(P)$.
 $[KS_{gfr}(P)]^c \subseteq KS_{gint}(P) \cup KS_{gint}(P^c)$.

$$(ii) \quad [KS_{gfr}(KS_{gint}(P))] \subseteq KS_{gcl}(KS_{gint}(P)) \cap KS_{gcl}(KS_{gint}(P^c)) \text{ [by(1)]}$$

$$\subseteq KS_{gcl}(KS_{gint}(P)) \cap KS_{gcl}((KS_{gcl}(P^c))^c)^c$$

$$\subseteq KS_{gcl}(KS_{gint}(P)) \cap KS_{gcl}(P^c)$$

$$\subseteq KS_{gcl}(P) \cap KS_{gcl}(P^c)$$

$$\subseteq KS_{gfr}(P).$$

Thus $KS_{gfr}(KS_{gint}(P)) \subseteq KS_{gfr}(P)$.

$$(iii) \quad KS_{gfr}(KS_{gcl}(P)) \subseteq KS_{gcl}(P) \cap KS_{gcl}(KS_{gcl}(P^c)) \text{ [by (10.6) (1)]}$$

$$\subseteq KS_{gcl}(KS_{gcl}(P)) \cap KS_{gcl}[KS_{gcl}(P)]^c$$

Now, $P \subseteq KS_{gcl}(P)$ This implies that $KS_{gcl}(P)^c \subseteq P^c$
 $KS_{gcl}(KS_{gcl}(P^c)) \subseteq KS_{gcl}(P^c)$
 Hence, $KS_{gfr}(P) \subseteq KS_{gcl}(P) \cap KS_{gcl}(P^c)$
 $KS_{gfr}(KS_{gcl}(P)) \subseteq KS_{gfr}(P)$.

□

Theorem 6.8. Let P and Q be any two subset of KSTS of $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$, then:

$$(i) \quad KS_{gsfr}(P \cup Q) \subseteq KS_{gsfr}(P) \cup KS_{gsfr}(Q).$$

$$(ii) \quad KS_{gsfr}(P \cap Q) \subseteq KS_{gsfr}(P) \cup KS_{gsfr}(Q).$$

Proof. (i) $KS_{gsfr}(P \cup Q) = KS_{gscl}(P \cup Q) \cap KS_{gscl}(P \cup Q)^c$ [by(10.6)(i)] = $(KS_{gscl}(P) \cup KS_{gscl}(Q)) \cap (P^c \cap Q^c) \subseteq (P \cup Q) \cap (KS_{gscl}(P^c) \cap KS_{gscl}(Q^c))$
 $\subseteq [KS_{gscl}(P) \cap KS_{gscl}(P^c) \cap KS_{gscl}(Q^c)] \cup [KS_{gscl}(Q) \cap KS_{gscl}(P^c) \cap KS_{gscl}(Q^c)]$
 $\subseteq [KS_{gsfr}(P) \cap KS_{gscl}(Q^c)] \cup [KS_{gsfr}(Q) \cap KS_{gscl}(P^c)]$ [by(10.6) (1)]
 $\subseteq KS_{gsfr}(P) \cup KS_{gsfr}(Q)$.

$$(ii) \quad KS_{gsfr}(P \cap Q) = KS_{gscl}(P \cap Q) \cap KS_{gscl}(P \cap Q)^c \text{ by(10.6)[i]} \quad KS_{gscl}(P) \cap KS_{gscl}(Q) \cap$$

$$KS_{gscl}(P^c \cap Q^c) \subseteq (KS_{gscl}(P) \cap KS_{gscl}(Q)) \cap (KS_{gscl}(P^c) \cup KS_{gscl}(Q^c))$$

$$\subseteq [KS_{gscl}(P) \cap KS_{gscl}(P^c) \cap KS_{gscl}(Q)] \cup [KS_{gscl}(Q) \cap KS_{gscl}(P^c) \cap KS_{gscl}(Q^c)]$$

$$\subseteq [KS_{gsfr}(P) \cap KS_{gscl}(Q)] \cup [KS_{gscl}(Q) \cap KS_{gsfr}(Q)] \text{ [by(10.6)(i)]}$$

$$\subseteq KS_{gsfr}(P) \cup KS_{gsfr}(Q).$$

□

Theorem 6.9. Let P and Q be any two subset of KSTS of $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$, then:

$$(i) \quad KS_{sgfr}(P \cup Q) \subseteq KS_{sgfr}(P) \cup KS_{sgfr}(Q).$$

$$(ii) \quad KS_{sgfr}(P \cap Q) \subseteq KS_{sgfr}(P) \cup KS_{sgfr}(Q).$$

Proof. (i) $KS_{sgfr}(P \cup Q) = KS_{sgcl}(P \cup Q) \cap KS_{sgcl}(P \cup Q)^c$ by(10.6)[i] = $(KS_{sgcl}(P) \cup KS_{sgcl}(Q)) \cap (P^c \cap Q^c) \subseteq (P \cup Q) \cap (KS_{sgcl}(P^c) \cap KS_{sgcl}(Q^c))$
 $\subseteq [KS_{sgcl}(P) \cap KS_{sgcl}(P^c) \cap KS_{sgcl}(Q^c)] \cup [KS_{sgcl}(Q) \cap KS_{sgcl}(P^c) \cap KS_{sgcl}(Q^c)]$
 $\subseteq [KS_{sgfr}(P) \cap KS_{sgcl}(Q^c)] \cup [KS_{sgfr}(Q) \cap KS_{sgcl}(P^c)]$ [by(10.6)(i)]
 $\subseteq KS_{sgfr}(P) \cup KS_{sgfr}(Q)$.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{(ii)} \quad & KS_{sgfr}(P \cap Q) = KS_{sgcl}(P \cap Q) \cap KS_{sgcl}(P \cap Q)^c \text{ by (10.6)[i]} \quad KS_{sgcl}(P) \cap KS_{sgcl}(Q) \cap \\
& KS_{sgcl}(P^c \cap Q^c) \subseteq (KS_{sgcl}(P) \cap KS_{sgcl}(Q)) \cap (KS_{sgcl}(P^c) \cup KS_{sgcl}(Q^c)) \\
& \subseteq [KS_{sgcl}(P) \cap KS_{sgcl}(P^c) \cap KS_{sgcl}(Q)] \cup [KS_{sgcl}(Q) \cap KS_{sgcl}(Q) \cap KS_{sgcl}(Q^c)] \\
& \subseteq [KS_{sgfr}(P) \cap KS_{sgcl}(Q)] \cup [KS_{sgcl}(Q) \cap KS_{sgfr}(Q)] \text{ [by (10.6)(i)]} \\
& \subseteq KS_{sgfr}(P) \cup KS_{sgfr}(Q).
\end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 6.10. Let P be a subset of a KSTS $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$. Then:

- (i) If P is $KS - O$, then $KS_{fr}(P) = KS_{cl}(P) - P$.
- (ii) $KS_{fr}(P) = \phi$ if and only if P is $KS - O$ as well as $KS - C$.
- (iii) P is $KS - O$ if and only if $P \cap KS_{fr}(P) = \phi$.
- (iv) P is $KS - C$ if and only if $KS_{fr}(P) \subseteq P$.

Proof. (i) By (9.1), $KS_{fr}(P) = KS_{cl}(P) - KS_{int}(P)$. P is $KS - O$ that implies $KS_{int}(P) = P$. Hence $KS_{fr}(P) = KS_{cl}(P) - P$.

(ii) Let $KS_{fr}(P) = \phi$. Then $KS_{fr}(P) = \phi$ this implies that $KS_{cl}(P) - KS_{int}(P) = \phi$. $KS_{cl}(P) = KS_{int}(P) = P$. P is $KS - O$ as well as closed. Conversely, let P be $KS - O$ as well as closed. $KS_{fr}(P) = KS_{cl}(P) - KS_{int}(P)$. Since P is $KS - C$, $KS_{cl}(P) = P$. Since P is $KS - O$, $KS_{int}(P) = P$. Hence $KS_{fr}(P) = \phi$.

(iii) By (9.1), we know that $KS_{fr}(P) = KS_{cl}(P) \cap KS_{cl}(P^c) = KS_{cl}(P) - KS_{int}(P)$. Let P be $KS - O$. Hence P^c is $KS - C$. $KS_{cl}(P^c) = P^c$. Now, $P \cap KS_{fr}(P) = P \cap (KS_{cl}(P) \cap KS_{cl}(P^c)) = P \cap (KS_{cl}(P) \cap ((P^c)^c)) = (P \cap (KS_{cl}(P))) \cap (P^c) = P \cap P^c = \phi$.
Conversely, let $P \cap KS_{fr}(P) = \phi$. This implies that $P \cap (KS_{cl}(P) \cap KS_{cl}(P^c)) = \phi$
 $\Rightarrow (P \cap (KS_{cl}(P) \cap KS_{cl}(P^c))) = \phi. \Rightarrow KS_{cl}(P^c) = P^c \Rightarrow P^c$ is KS_{closed} . P is $KS - O$.

(iv) Let P be $KS - C$. Then $KS_{cl}(P) = P$. Hence $KS_{fr}(P) = KS_{cl}(P) - KS_{cl}(P^c) = P \cap KS_{cl}(P^c)$. So that $KS_{fr}(P) \subseteq P$.
Conversely, let $KS_{fr}(P) \subseteq P$. Then $P \cup KS_{fr}(P) = P$. But $P \cup KS_{fr}(P) = KS_{cl}(P)$. That is $P = KS_{cl}(P)$. Hence P is $KS - C$.

□

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